

EasyWalk: An Intelligent Social Walker for active living

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Abstract—Fall-related injuries pose a growing concern for the elderly in Western Europe, often leading to a fear of falling that confines many people to their homes, limiting their mobility. Unfortunately, extended periods of immobilization can have adverse effects on their musculoskeletal health. While walkers are recommended for fall prevention, their adoption is hindered by cost and usability issues. The EasyWalk project seeks to tackle these challenges by developing an affordable, user-friendly, and safe smart walker. Current smart walkers face reliability issues, lack in human-machine interaction, and come with high costs. EasyWalk plans to equip its smart walker with cost-effective sensors, enabling safe navigation in complex environments without the need for predefined maps. It will decode user intentions based on leg movements and handlebar forces, fostering improved interaction between the user and the walker through shared intelligence.

Index Terms—smart-walker, human-robot interaction, intelligent robotics, neurorobotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Fall-related injuries are a significant health concern for elderly, especially in Western Europe, where the incidence and mortality rates are high. In 2017, various countries reported medical treatment sought by older adults due to falls, ranging from 7594 to 19796 cases per 100000 people. Falls are becoming more common as the elderly population grows, affecting about one-third of people aged 65 and above annually [1].

Falls not only result in physical injuries but also have significant psychological repercussions, with the fear of falling adversely affecting the quality of life, including physical activity, social engagement, and mental health [2]. Consequently, elderly prefer to age in place at home, but prolonged immobilization can have detrimental effects on their musculoskeletal system, leading to poor posture control, muscle weakness, and altered walking mechanics [3].

Addressing these mobility impairments is crucial for maintaining independence and improving the quality of life, with far-reaching implications for social, healthcare policies, and

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the economy. In this context, walkers are commonly recommended as fall-prevention assistive devices to enhance stability, mobility, and confidence in daily activities [4]. These devices work by expanding the base of support and facilitating stabilizing reactions.

Recent technological advancements have enabled the integration of sensors and actuators into walkers, transforming them into *smart walkers*. These smart walkers can be categorized based on their autonomy, shared-control capabilities, and various functionalities, such as manual guidance, sit-to-stand assistance, and user state monitoring. There is a distinction between motorized and passive walkers, with motorized ones offering autonomous navigation and passive ones relying on sensors and brakes to guide users [5]–[9].

Despite significant research and development in this field, the widespread adoption of smart walkers in daily life remains limited due to factors like cost, size, control interface, and lack of customization for individual users [7]. The EasyWalk project aims to address these challenges by reimagining smart walkers to foster a stronger human-robot interaction, and thus, to enhance trust between users and their assistive devices.

II. THE EASYWALK PROJECT

Over the past decade, numerous studies have proposed solutions for developing smart walkers. These approaches range from user-guided walkers with intelligent braking systems to autonomous platforms equipped with people detection modules and remote teleoperation capabilities, as described in the previous section. Despite considerable technological and scientific advancements in this field, the practical impact of current smart walkers remains limited. Three primary reasons account for this:

- **Reliability and Robustness:** Current approaches often lack reliability and robustness, particularly when used in daily life situations and natural environments. They struggle to perform consistently in real-world scenarios.
- **Human-Machine Interaction:** The interaction between humans and machines is frequently underestimated. In most cases, users either guide the walker or it operates

Fig. 1. (A) A commercial passive walker (left) and a prototype of active walker (right) equipped with navigation sensors. (B) Schematic representation of the modules devised in the EasyWalk project

autonomously, with minimal integration of the intentions of both the user and the machine.

- **Cost Barrier:** The cost of these platforms is often prohibitively high, hindering widespread adoption. This cost factor not only prevents continuous personal use at home but also jeopardizes user trust, especially among elderly.

The EasyWalk project grounds on the hypothesis that trust in smart walkers can be established by creating an affordable, user-friendly, reliable device capable of understanding and contextualizing the user's intentions within the environment. To address these challenges, the project proposes innovative solutions rooted in human-robot interaction approaches, as depicted in Figure 1. Specifically, EasyWalk aims to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) Develop a smart walker equipped with a minimal set of cost-effective sensors, including a commercial RGB-D camera, low-cost laser range-finder, and force sensors.
- 2) Utilize data from these sensors to enable safe and social navigation in unfamiliar and cluttered environments, without relying on predefined global maps.
- 3) Infer the user's motion intentions, such as starting, stopping, and changing direction, from leg movements and forces applied to the walker's handlebar.
- 4) Integrate user and robotic intelligence through a novel shared-intelligence approach, leveraging techniques like artificial potential fields and model predictive control to enhance trust and cooperation.

We expect that achieving these goals will result in the creation of an innovative smart walker capable of interpreting user intentions while ensuring safe navigation. Additionally, it is expected that improving the interaction between the user and the walker will enhance ease of use and, consequently, user trust in this robotic device.

III. CONCLUSION

The EasyWalk project seeks to demonstrate how intelligent robotic devices can restore independence in daily activities. This can lead to clinical benefits such as improved sensory functions, better health, enhanced body perception, and reduced risk of mood disorders. Furthermore, promoting independent mobility, especially in the elderly, can prevent cognitive decline and enhance the quality of life for users and their families.

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